

TECHNOSTRESS INHIBITORS AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE: INFLUENCE ON LIBRARY STAFF'S WELL-BEING IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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ABSTRACT

In an era of increasing reliance on technology, understanding the influence of technostress and the importance of work-life balance on staff well-being is crucial for creating a supportive work environment. This study aimed to investigate the relationship among technostress inhibitors, work-life balance, and the well-being of library staff. Work-life balance plays a vital role in determining the overall well-being of employees. There were 97 library staff who participated in the study. Total enumeration was employed as sampling method. A survey questionnaire was utilized to collect the data. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that the library staff assessment of the technostress inhibitors in terms of literacy facilitation, technical support provision, and involvement facilitation was high; the library staff's work-life balance was high; and the level of the library staff's well-being in terms of job satisfaction, living satisfaction, and psychological well-being is generally high. Moreover, the library staff's assessment of technostress inhibitors in terms of literacy facilitation, technical support provision, and involvement facilitation and their work-life balance significantly influence their well-being. These findings confirm the conceptual model of Ragu-Nathan et al. (2019). Drawing the inference, effective technostress management practices and supportive work-life balance initiatives contribute to higher job satisfaction, living satisfaction, psychological well-being and the overall well-being among library staff. It is recommended that the librarians may take advantage of the available training and support resources to become proficient in the latest technologies used in the library.

Keywords: *Work-Life Balance, Technostress Inhibitors, Psychological Well-Being, Library Staff*

INTRODUCTION

As a result, people are experiencing information overload due to the overwhelming amount of data that is readily available to them, a consequence of the rapid proliferation of digital information. Because of their line of work, library employees are among the people who are constantly inundated with information. They have the difficult responsibility of sorting through enormous volumes of digital content while making sure that it is accurate and relevant for their customers. Library employees may experience cognitive overload, lower productivity, and higher stress levels as a result of this ongoing exposure to information overload (Abowha, 2022).

The usage of electronic resources and novel search tactics has made it necessary for library employees to continuously learn and adapt in order to keep up with the most recent tools and approaches. This ongoing desire to learn and up skilling can cause worry and anxiety, particularly for employees who might feel unprepared or unable to handle the demands of new technological improvement.

Technostress has resulted from the library's digital transition, information expansion, changing resources, and new search techniques, which may have an impact on worker welfare. On the other hand, personnel may have less harmful consequences from technostress if they take inhibitors of technostress. Technostress inhibitors are methods, approaches, or resources that people can use to lessen and manage the consequences of technological strain. Brennan, M. (2020) described that technostress, a prevalent issue in the digital age, can negatively impact employees' mental and physical well-being. To mitigate this, implementing technostress inhibitors like setting boundaries, practicing digital detoxes, and seeking social support is imperative.

Considering the aforementioned viewpoint, preserving a healthy balance between Personal and professional lives can enhance wellbeing. The failure to keep oneself in a healthy. A person may experience low psychological well-being as a result of work-life balance. Not succeeding failing to achieve the required balance has a detrimental effect on mental health, which can cause family strife, despair, and burnout (Yang, 2018). Prasad and According to Saraswati, K. and Lie, D. (2020), psychological wellness is impacted by work-life balance.

This study assumes that technostress inhibitors and work-life balance influence individual well-being. This assumption draws upon the theoretical framework established. Technostress Creators and Inhibitors, which lays the foundation for understanding how work-life balance and technostress inhibitors can both improve well-being in a technologically advanced society. According to Tarafdar et al. (2019), technostress is the stress that people experience as a result of using information and communication technology and systems. Technostress producing variables include things like job uncertainty and overload related to information and communications technology, and other ICT complexities associated to ICT usage. Technostress inhibitors are the mechanisms that might reduce overall technostress (Rangu-Nathan, 2019). This study focused on the conceptual model of Technostress Inhibitors. In effect, the conceptual model of technostress creators and inhibitors may provide a valuable framework in

understanding the influence of technology on work-life balance and well-being. By examining both the positive influences surrounding technology use, in a world where technology is pervasive, this approach can direct actions to support healthier and more balanced lives. Furthermore, resources that can lower employee ICT usage and results connected to job stress are referred to as technostress inhibitors. In the same way, organizational procedures and mechanisms that assist in reducing the adverse impacts of ICT use are known as inhibitors.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study makes the assumption that work-life balance and technological stress reducers have an impact on people's wellbeing. This presumption is based on the theoretical framework developed by Ragu-Nathan et al.'s (2008) model, Technostress Creators and Inhibitors, which establishes the knowledge of how work-life balance enhances well-being in a technologically advanced world and how technostress inhibitors can reduce technostress.

According to Tarafdar et al. (2019), technostress is the stress that people experience as a result of using information and communication technologies and systems. Technostress creators include things like job insecurity related to technology, overload related to technology, and other technical difficulties arising from the use of technology. The mechanisms that could lessen overall technostress are known as technostress inhibitors (Tarafdar, Tu, & Ragu-Nathan, 2011) The Technostress Inhibitors conceptual model was the main focus of this investigation. Essentially, the theoretical construct of technostress generators and deterrents could offer a useful structure for comprehending how technology impacts well-being and work-life equilibrium. Through an analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of technology use, this model can direct efforts to support more balanced and healthy lifestyles in a world where technology permeates every aspect of daily life. Furthermore, resources that can lower employee ICT usage and outcomes related to job stress are referred to as technostress inhibitors.

In the same way, organizational procedures and mechanisms that assist in reducing the adverse effects of ICT use are known as inhibitors. These mechanisms include end-user training, technical assistance, and user involvement in the development and deployment of new ICT solutions. Organizational mechanisms that lower technostress foster communication, fortify a culture of support, and increase innovation, claim Tarafdar et al. (2019). Richardson (2017). Conceptualized technostress inhibitors as consisting of three main categories or components: literacy facilitation, technical support and involvement facilitation. Each of these three mechanisms has the potential to reduce the effect of technostress creators on strain-related ICT outcomes for employees.

The first inhibitor of stress is ***Literacy facilitation***. This inhibitor refers to mechanisms that increase employee levels of ICT literacy (e.g., establishment of a close relationship with the IS department and encouragement of ICT knowledge sharing among co-workers). According to Aktan & Toraman (2022), literacy facilitation describes mechanisms that encourage and foster the sharing of ICTs related knowledge between individuals, where it enables them to cope with the demand of learning new ICTs programs. Literacy facilitation reduces technostress because it helps users to understand

the ICTs programs. Literacy facilitation involves improving individuals' knowledge and understanding of technology. By enhancing their digital literacy skills, they can feel more confident and competent when using technology, thereby, reducing the stress and anxiety associated with technological challenge through training programs, workshops, or online resources that provide guidance on using technology effectively (Tarafdar et al., 2019).

One way to implement literacy involvement in the library setting is to offer staff workshops and training sessions to help them improve their literacy skills. This could involve workshops on writing, research, and other literacy-related subjects in addition to instruction on new software or tools. Another would be to provide a range of reading materials, such as books, magazines, and newspapers, and create an atmosphere that highlights the value of literacy. They can also design areas like writing centers and quiet study spaces that are good for reading and writing. This could give the employees greater self-assurance and technological competence.

This is an additional technostress inhibitor. This inhibitor alludes to assistance mechanisms in the sense of formalized assistance. Initiatives for end-user assistance and technical support are offered to users to address their ICT problems and mitigate the effects of technostress. According to Stana, R., & Nicolajsen, H. W. (2021). IT workers should encourage users to experiment with new ICTs and offer helpdesk and technical support to address end-user issues. Having dependable technical support at hand can make it easier for people to diagnose and fix technical problems, which will lessen their stress and frustration. Tarafdar et al. (2019) state that by offering an easily accessible help desk manned by IT professionals, such support can reduce techno-uncertainty and techno-complexity. Organizations can provide help desks, IT support teams, or online for a where people can seek assistance with technology-related problems.

In a library setting, this could include providing access to a wide range of digital resources, such as e-books, audiobooks, and online databases, to support literacy development. . These resources can be accessed through library websites, mobile apps, and other digital platforms, making it easier for patrons to access and engage with reading materials. In order to support their patrons' literacy development, libraries can also provide online tutorials, webinars, and interactive exercises. These resources are available via the library's website or via collaborations with organizations and educational institutions. All of these could lessen the stress brought on by technical difficulties and problems, allowing library employees to feel supported and less overburdened by the demands of technology.

Moreover, the third inhibitor of technostress is ***Involvement facilitation*** referring to mechanisms that strengthen employee 's engagement in new technology (e.g., incentive systems connected to usage and participation in process changes). Roskova and Cova (2022) opined that involvement facilitation helps alleviate technostress by keeping users informed about the rationale for introducing new ICTs and by letting them know about the effects of such introduction, and by encouraging them to use and experiment with new ICTs. Organizations can empower people to feel more in control of how they use technology by involving them in decision-making processes, offering

opportunities for feedback and input, and fostering an inclusive and supportive technological environment. Encouraging people to actively participate in technology-related activities can help lower technostress and improve people's general well-being (Walton, 2019). This is also consistent with research conducted by Lorrain (2020) and Singh et al. (2022) showing the relationship and impact of technostress inhibitors on employees' personal and professional well-being.

Including library employees in the development, selection, and application of new technologies increases their sense of empowerment and engagement. Employees can participate in focus groups, feedback sessions, or project teams to offer their opinions and suggestions on the new technologies. Moreover, fostering a collaborative and knowledge-sharing atmosphere within the workplace can aid in the decrease of technostress. Staff members will feel more supported and less overwhelmed by the demands of new technologies if regular team meetings, knowledge-sharing sessions, and collaborative projects are implemented.

Through the implementation of literacy facilitation, technical support, and involvement facilitation, people can effectively handle and overcome the stressors that are linked to technology use. These stress-reduction technologies seek to enhance people's understanding, offer the assistance they require, and cultivate a feeling of empowerment and engagement, ultimately lowering technological stress and enhancing wellbeing. These inhibitors of technological stress can help lower technological stress and improve participants' general well-being (Walton, 2019).

By leveraging technology through literacy facilitation, technical support, and involvement facilitation, individuals can better manage and cope with the stressors associated with the use of technology. These technostress inhibitors aim to improve individuals' knowledge, provide necessary support, and foster a sense of control and involvement, ultimately reducing technostress and promoting well-being. These technostress inhibitors can help reduce technostress and enhance overall well-being of the participants (Walton, 2019). This study adopted two meanings of WLB. The first is the definition given by Adisa, T.A., Gbadamosi, and Mordi, C.(2019) which refer to WLB as encompassing several initiatives design to help employees to balance the competing demands of paid work and private lives. The second meaning is the one developed by Lewis and Beauregard (2018) relating WLB to the complex and dynamic interaction between paid employment and non- work life domains. This study focuses on the work-life balance (WLB) of library staff, highlighting the importance of maintaining balance between professional activities and personal life to ensure a balanced relationship.

While work-life balance guarantees that people have time and energy for their personal lives outside of work, technostress inhibitors help people cope with the stresses associated with technology. By taking these things into consideration, businesses can a nurturing workplace that improves psychological health and cultivates employee well-being. People who have access to technology-enhanced stress relievers and manage their work and personal lives well are likely to report feeling less stressed, more satisfied with their jobs, having better mental health, and feeling better overall. Increased

engagement, productivity, and general job performance may follow from this. It is imperative that organizations acknowledge the importance of these variables and put strategies in place to assist staff in balancing work and personal life and managing technostress. By putting employees' well-being first, businesses can foster a positive workplace culture that improves psychological health and boosts overall business success.

In the context of technostress inhibitors, psychological well-being can be affected by these inhibitors on organizational resources that help reduce the negative effects of techno-stressors on employees. Technostress inhibitors, which act as a buffer against the negative effects of techno-stressors, have been linked to employees' psychological well-being, according to a number of studies (Dai et al., 2021; Tement et al. 2020; & Trafadar et al., 2019). For instance, a study by Hang et al. (2023) discovered that technostress inhibitors are anticipated to have a dual function, as they are positively correlated with the psychological well-being of employees and act as a buffer against the detrimental effects of technological stressors. This suggests that the presence of technostress inhibitors in the workplace can enhance employees' psychological health. Thus, the emphasis in the context of technostress inhibitors is on comprehending how The organizational resources of the technostress inhibitors can protect workers' psychological health from the negative effects of technostress.

Regarding the library, it is widely recognized that librarians are the frontline staff who maintain the vitality and functionality of libraries. They do, however, frequently deal with particular technostress issues that may be detrimental to their mental health. Libraries can prioritize the psychological well-being of their staff and create a supportive environment by implementing technostress inhibitors. By fostering a supportive atmosphere, lowering technological stress, and boosting positive user experiences, libraries can support the psychological well-being of their staff members and build a stronger, more resilient library community.

Meanwhile, the harmony between our personal and professional lives is greatly influenced by the strong and complex relationship between psychological well-being and work-life balance (Saraswati & Lie, 2020). A more harmonious balance between work and personal life can directly result from improved psychological well-being, and vice versa. The relationship is a two-way street. Improved emotional regulation abilities are directly related to psychological well-being. Resilience is fostered by a solid psychological foundation, which enables people to overcome obstacles at work without feeling overwhelmed. This makes it possible for them to establish sound boundaries and uphold them in the face of adversity.

It's critical to keep in mind that there is reciprocal influence between psychological health and work-life balance. Achieving a healthy work-life balance requires psychological well-being. People can develop the abilities and resources necessary to more easily manage the demands of both work and personal life by fostering mental health and emotional resilience. contentment, resulting in a life that is more balanced and meaningful (Saraswati & Lie, 2020).

Psychological well-being can be promoted in the context of technology by addressing technostress and promoting the inhibitors. The development of technostress has been linked to employees' psychological health. Previous studies have indicated that the demands placed on employees' jobs by technology in the workplace can have a detrimental effect on their psychological health (Borowiec et. al.,2022). According to the study, employees who are unable to effectively manage their work using the latest technological advancements may experience technostress creators. Technostress inhibitors have the ability to reduce the adverse effects of technology while safeguarding psychological health.

It is possible to preserve and improve the psychological health of library staff members in the workplace by encouraging literacy facilitation, offering technical assistance, and easing participation in digital activities. Putting policies in place to the psychological health of library employees can be considerably enhanced by addressing technostress and realizing its significance (Delmo & Dequito, 2023).

Additionally, this helps to establish a favorable workplace that encourages efficiency and productivity, guaranteeing the survival of library services in the digital. Particularly in the context of technology use, the conceptual model of technostress inhibitors provides a useful framework for comprehending how psychological well-being can influence and be influenced by work-life balance. These links develop as follows. Misuse and overuse of technology can result in Technostress is defined as weariness, frustration, and anxiety associated with using technology.

The following are some ways that this technostress can impair psychological health: first, because work demands and continuous connectivity can invade personal time, making it challenging to switch off and relax; second, the pressure to be available and responsive to technology at all times can result in work overload; and third, feeling overpowered by technology can reduce one's sense of control over one's personal and professional lives, which affects both. Mitigating these negative impacts of technology are the technostress inhibitors that protect psychological wellbeing. By addressing technostress and promoting these inhibitors, individuals can ultimately achieve psychological well-being. This positive mental state then plays a crucial role in maintaining work-life balance.

Work-life balance refers to an ideal condition in which an employee can divide their time, energy, or attention between work and other vital elements of their life (Greenhaus, J. H., et. al., 2023) It is associated with psychological well-being as it has a profound impact on how individuals navigate the often-demanding juggling act of work and personal life (Borowiec & Drygas, 2022). Good psychological well-being equips individuals with better tools to manage stress, anxiety, and negativity arising from work. It has been pointed out that a strong psychological foundation makes individuals more resilient in the face of work challenges (Delmo & Dequito, 2023).

Furthermore, in the digital age, the connection between librarians' psychological health and work-life balance becomes even more nuanced. Their equilibrium and general well-being may also be jeopardized by technostress, which is defined as the physical and

mental strain brought on by using technology. The presence of technostress inhibitors can act as countermeasures, creating a healthier work environment. While some studies may show that there may not be a direct correlation between work-life balance and librarians' psychological well-being, maintaining a healthy work-life balance is still crucial for overall well-being. Employers and employees in various professions can benefit from implementing strategies that promote work-life balance, stress management, and wellness programs to support librarians' well-being. From the foregoing discussion, this study focused on exploring the relationship between technostress inhibitors (literacy facilitation, technical support provision, and involvement facilitation) and the library staff's well-being (job satisfaction, living satisfaction, and psychological well-being) in the digital age.

The theory, concepts, and studies discussed provided new and valuable insights and essential ideas that helped the researcher arrive at the assumption that techno with that technostress inhibitors and work-life balance influence library staff well-being. It is within this framework that this study has been conceptualized, and Figure 1 shows the interplay of the variables.

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation of the Study

Research Objective

This study aimed to explore how factors such as technostress inhibitors, which are strategies or interventions to mitigate the negative effects of technology-related stress, and work-life balance, which refers to the equilibrium between work responsibilities and personal life, influence the overall well-being of library staff members.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive correlational research design. The correlational methods are commonly used to assess the relationship between variables (Darshini et. Al (2021). Additionally, correlational studies are examined to determine descriptive or predictive

relationships. In this study, the researcher will be investigating the relationship between technostress inhibitors and work-life balance as predictors of library staff's wellbeing in the digital age. This study was participated by 97 library staff, 70 from Marawi city, 7 from MSU IIT, 3 from MSU Naawan and 17 from Bangsamoro Library and Archives. Convince sampling was used in the study often used to assess how well variables are correlated (Darshini et. Al. ,2021). Further, descriptive and predictive relationship are sought after via correlational research. Who are willing and able to take in the study.

Table 1. Summary Table of Assessment of the Technostress Inhibitor

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Literacy Facilitation	3.97	High	0.70
Technical Support Provision	3.70	High	0.69
Involvement Facilitation	3.83	High	0.74
Overall Assessment	3.83	High	0.62

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the summary table of well-being in terms of Job satisfaction, Living satisfaction and Psychological well-being. The data show that the well-being of the participants considering the Job satisfaction, Living satisfaction and Psychological well-being were generally rated as “high”.

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	31	31.96
3.51-4.50	High	32	32.99
2.51-3.50	Moderate	34	35.05
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.0
	Total	97	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.97	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.70	

The three aspects of literacy facilitation, technical support provision, and involvement facilitation work together to create a supportive environment that empowers library staff to navigate technology effectively. Literacy facilitation refers to programs and resources that help employees develop the skills and knowledge needed to use technology

effectively. It can include training, workshops, user guides, and readily available resources. By increasing digital literacy, employees feel more confident and competent in using technology, reducing anxiety and frustration associated with technostress. Technical support provision refers to readily available technical support, whether through dedicated IT staff, online resources, or peer-to-peer troubleshooting channels. Knowing that help is readily available reduces feelings of helplessness and isolation when facing technical difficulties. Efficient support minimizes downtime and frustrations associated with technostress.

Involvement facilitation: refers to practices that encourage employee participation in decisions and discussions regarding technology implementation. Feeling involved fosters a sense of control and ownership. When employees understand the "why" behind technology adoption and have a say in "how" it's implemented, they are more likely to embrace it, reducing resistance and technostress. The studies of Brennan (2020) showcase the effectiveness of a multi-faceted approach that combines literacy facilitation, technical support provision, and involvement facilitation. By addressing both technical skills and user experience, organizations can significantly reduce technostress and foster a more positive and productive work environment for employees using new technologies

Table 2. Summary Table of well-being.

Dimensions of Well-being	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Job Satisfaction	3.82	High	0.71
Living Satisfaction	3.65	High	0.74
Psychological Well-being	3.92	High	0.71
Overall	3.80	High	0.61

The summary table of well-being in terms of Job satisfaction, Living satisfaction and Psychological well-being. The data show that the well-being of the participants considering the Job satisfaction, Living satisfaction and Psychological well-being were generally rated as "high". This findings reflect a positive work environment and supportive organizational culture within the library, which contributes to the overall well-being of the staff. Daluma (2022) points out that it is important for library management to continue fostering a supportive work environment, recognizing the achievements and contributions of staff, and providing opportunities for growth and development. By prioritizing staff well-being, libraries can cultivate a positive and effective workforce, leading to enhanced service delivery and overall organizational success.

Table 3. *Regression Analysis of the Influence of Participants' Assessment of Technostress Inhibitors and their Work-life Balance on their Well-being*

Table 3 presents the regression analysis of the influence of participants' assessment of technostress inhibitors and their work-life balance towards their well-being. Data revealed that the whole model is significant ($F = 43.83, p = .000$), implying that participants who highly assessed the technostress inhibitors and whose work-life balance are high, also have high level of well-being. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Furthermore, 47.2 percent of the variability in their well-being can be accounted for by a combination of their assessment of technostress inhibitors and work-life balance. The remaining 52.8 percent can be attributed to additional factors not included in this study, such as social support, a strong network of friends and family, and support systems in both the personal and professional spheres. Additionally, the balance between job demands and available resources can have an impact on well-being. Greater well-being is a result of sufficient resources and reasonable expectations.

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.579	.361		1.60	.112
Assessment of Technostress Inhibitors	.423	.094	.430	4.50**	.000
Work-life Balance	.460	.130	.338	3.53**	.001
Model Summary					
R = .695 R ² = .483 Adjusted R ² = .472 F = 43.83** p = .000					

In terms of the individual independent variables, their assessment of technostress inhibitors came out as having the highest influence on their well-being, showing that for every unit increase in their assessment of these inhibitors, there is a corresponding .423 increase in their well-being (B=.423, t= 4.50, p=.000).

As indicated by the unstandardized coefficient (B = 0.423), for every unit increase in the assessment of technostress inhibitors, there is a corresponding increase of 0.423 in the participants' well-being. This suggests that the more participants recognize and utilize technostress inhibitors, the higher they rate their well-being. Moreover, work-life balance also significantly influences their well-being. To support the claim that the assessment of technostress inhibitors has the highest influence on well-being. Tarafdar et al. (2019) explored technostress's negative effects on well-being, emphasizing the need for inhibitors to mitigate its detrimental effects.

Conclusions

The present study was centered on exploring the relationship between technostress inhibitors and the library staff's well-being in the digital age. Evidently, the study reveals that technology has become a crucial part of library services as technostress inhibitors positively impact staff well-being.

This finding confirms the conceptual model of Rangu-Nathan et al. (2019) that guided this study, where both technostress creators and inhibitors, as a conceptual model, offered the hypothesis on how work-life balance and technostress inhibitors affect wellbeing. This

study emphasized the significance of work-life balance and technostress inhibitors in predicting the well-being of library employees. Moreover, technostress inhibitors helped in enhancing library staff's knowledge, support, and control, thereby reducing technostress and promoting overall well-being. It can be inferred that effective technostress management practices and supportive work-life balance initiatives can contribute to higher job satisfaction, living satisfaction, psychological well-being and the overall well-being among library staff. Librarians who have a good WLB are less likely to experience stress and burnout, which can contribute to higher levels of job satisfaction. Also, librarians who have clear communication about technology-related expectations and goals are more likely to experience higher levels of job satisfaction. Recognizing the importance of these factors and implementing appropriate measures to address technostress benefits the psychological well-being of the library staff. This enables them to set healthy boundaries and maintain personal boundaries even under pressure.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion derived from the study, the following recommendations are offered for considerations:

1. For **Library Administrators**. The current initiatives that offer technical support (consistent help with tech concerns), literacy facilitation (training on new technologies), and engagement facilitation (opportunities for staff input on tech deployment) may be kept and strengthened. They might also think about doing recurring staff polls to find out where technostress inhibitors could be improved.
2. For **Librarians**. They can learn how to use the newest technology in the library by making use of the training and assistance materials that are offered. This will enable the support of colleagues who are under technostress and serve as an example of the usefulness of these services. Furthermore, they might encourage candid communication and teamwork among the relevant departments, which can aid in fostering a feeling of support and belonging, lowering stress levels, and enhancing general wellbeing.
3. For **Faculty**. It is possible for them to contemplate their pivotal function in upholding a favorable work milieu through the promotion of cooperation, candid communication, and gratitude towards peers. Additionally, they can leverage existing resources to effectively handle technological stress and preserve a salubrious work-life equilibrium.
4. For **future Researchers**. They might investigate how these work-life balance programs and technostress inhibitors affect employees' well-being in the long run. Examine the particular features of each inhibitor that have the biggest impact on lowering technostress. Further investigation into the particular requirements of various library staff roles may be necessary to further customize tech-stress reduction techniques.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In accordance with research protocol, the paper was submitted, reviewed and approved by the College's Research and Ethics Committee.

This study adhered to the Republic Act No. 10173 of the Philippines, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which mandates that all participants' information and data were treated with utmost confidentiality. Information was coded and did not have a direct correlation identifying the participants. Only the researcher knew the participant code number. The data collected was kept in an encrypted computer file. It was also made clear data would be used for research purpose only. The participants' informed consent were taken with a confidentiality guarantee of protection against unauthorized use of their data.

This research had minimal risks. No personal and confidential information were asked and participation was voluntary and anonymous. Participants could withdraw their participation at any time if a question made them uncomfortable and they did not have to give any reason for not responding to any question.

Only eligible participants were selected and in compliance with this, inclusion criteria was not based on race, ethnicity, and socioeconomic class but ensured that only qualified persons were selected as participants and in this study only the library staff of the institution were selected. The potential benefits of participating include contributing valuable knowledge on technostress and work-life balance, which can ultimately lead to improved workplace practices and employee well-being.

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